

GASLIGHTING AND JOB SATISFACTION IN EMPLOYEES WORKING IN THE CORPORATE SECTOR; THE MODERATING ROLE OF GENDER

Nazia Shahan^{*1}, Kainat Fateh Ali²

^{*1}Management Trainee Officer at Human Resource Department, ALM Outsourcing Services (Pvt.) Limited, Lahore

²Department of Applied Psychology, Student at School of Professional Psychology, University of University of Management and Technology, Lahore.

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Corresponding Author: *

Nazia Shahan

Abstract

This study examined the impact of organizational gaslighting on job satisfaction, with gender considered as a potential moderator. Drawing on Human Relations Theory, two dimensions of gaslighting, Trivialization and Affliction, were assessed among 401 employees in Pakistan using a correlational cross-sectional design. Reliability analysis indicated acceptable internal consistency for both dimensions, though average variance extracted (AVE) values suggested convergent validity. Discriminant validity, tested through HTMT ratios, was satisfactory. Structural model results showed that neither Trivialization nor Affliction significantly predicted job satisfaction, and gender did not moderate these relationships. The predictors accounted for only 5.4% of the variance in job satisfaction ($R^2 = .054$). These findings suggest that gaslighting may influence job satisfaction indirectly and that broader organizational and psychosocial variables should be explored. Practical implications emphasize the importance of anti-gaslighting policies and supportive workplace climates to protect employee well-being.

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is universally recognized as a critical pillar underpinning employee well-being, organizational productivity, and economic stability. According to the 2021 Gallup State of the Global Workplace report, nearly 23% of workers worldwide are thriving at work, marking the highest level of workplace happiness since Gallup began tracking this metric in 2009 (Gallup, Inc., 2021). Despite this, the global employee engagement rate remains low at 21%, highlighting the persistent challenges organizations face in fostering sustained employee satisfaction and motivation (Gallup, Inc., 2021). Contrasting these global trends, Pakistan reports an impressive 43% of employees expressing high job satisfaction, a figure that suggests distinctive local labor market dynamics shaped by cultural and economic factors (Gallup Pakistan, 2024).

Nevertheless, many employees in Pakistan and globally continue to encounter toxic workplace behavior, including gaslighting, a subtle yet damaging form of psychological manipulation that causes individuals to question their own perceptions and value (Wang et al., 2025). While extensively studied in personal and clinical psychology, gaslighting in the professional environment remains under-researched despite its likely detrimental impact on job satisfaction and mental health. Moreover, gender plays a significant role in how gaslighting affects job satisfaction, reflecting broader societal and workplace norms that influence men's and women's experiences differently (Patterson & Matias, 2025).

These are explain through the Human Relations Theory introduced by Mayo (1933) which emphasizes

the significance of social relationships, employee well-being, and supportive leadership in promoting organizational effectiveness. This theory highlights that employees are not merely economic beings but social individuals whose productivity is influenced by their feelings, attitudes, and interpersonal interactions within the workplace. It underscores the importance of psychological factors such as trust, communication, recognition, and participative management in fostering motivation and job satisfaction. By focusing on human-centric management, the theory advocates for leadership styles that nurture positive social dynamics, enhance employee morale, and facilitate cooperative behavior. The Human Relations Theory provides a foundational framework for understanding the detrimental impact of workplace gaslighting, as such behaviors violate the core tenets of respect, empathy, and open communication necessary for healthy work environments.

This study aims to investigate the impact of gaslighting on job satisfaction, with special attention to gender as a moderating factor. The findings are expected to provide valuable insights that can inform organizational policies and interventions designed to foster healthier, more equitable work environments, thus benefiting both employees and employers.

Literature review

Organizational gaslighting is a subtle but harmful form of workplace abuse where supervisors manipulate or distort reality to undermine employees' confidence and perceptions. Recent research conceptualizes gaslighting as involving two main dimensions: Trivialization of the employee's experiences and direct affliction causing psychological harm (Hassan et al., 2024). It is linked to decreased work motivation, job embeddedness, and negative emotional outcomes, highlighting its detrimental impact on employee well-being and organizational outcomes (Wang et al., 2025). Supervisory gaslighting damages employees' affective organizational commitment and can trigger burnout and turnover intentions, especially in high-stress professions such as nursing (Moisoglou et al., 2025). The recently developed Gaslighting at Work Scale (GWS) validates these harmful effects and identifies loss of self-trust

and abuse of power as core facets of gaslighting (Katsiroumpa et al., 2025)

Further, gaslighting behavior has been shown to significantly increase role conflict, which in turn reduces job satisfaction and heightens workplace stress (Aurangzeb et al., 2023). The subtle nature of gaslighting often leads to underreporting but creates a toxic work environment detrimental to occupational health (Pandey et al., 2023).

Gender plays a crucial role in understanding variances in job satisfaction across contexts. Historical gender-job satisfaction paradoxes where women reported higher satisfaction despite wage disparities are now seen as nuanced by socio-economic and workplace variables (El-Sayed et al., 2025). Women in secure or formalized job sectors tend to report higher satisfaction, attributed to workplace supports and benefits (Patterson & Matias, 2025). Work-life balance and intrinsic job rewards reduce observable gender differences in satisfaction (Atta et al., 2024).

Furthermore, men and women react differently to incentive structures and workplace culture, underscoring the need for gender-responsive policies (El-Sayed et al., 2025).

Job satisfaction itself is conceptualized as a positive emotional state resulting from one's appraisal of job experiences and conditions (Montuori et al., 2022). Workplace abuse including gaslighting correlates with reduced satisfaction, increased burnout, and turnover (Hassan et al., 2024; Sim & Jeong, 2025). Increasing evidence shows that gaslighting reduces motivation and organizational commitment, further eroding job satisfaction (Majumdarr et al., 2024; Orešković et al., 2023). Conversely, supportive environments that buffer gaslighting can foster higher job embeddedness and satisfaction (AlMarzooqi et al., 2025).

Rationale

Job satisfaction, defined as a positive emotional state resulting from an individual's appraisal of their job experiences and conditions (AlMarzooqi et al., 2025), remains a critical outcome in organizational behavior research due to its direct influence on employee well-being and organizational effectiveness. Despite this, workplace factors that detrimentally influence job satisfaction, such as organizational gaslighting, are underexplored. Gaslighting, characterized by a supervisor's Trivialization of

employees' experiences and infliction of psychological harm, has been linked to lowered job motivation, decreased affective organizational commitment, increased burnout, and higher turnover intentions (Pandey et al., 2023; El-Sayed et al., 2025). These negative outcomes highlight the corrosive effect of gaslighting on job satisfaction and overall employee psychological health (Moisoglou et al., 2025; Kukreja & Pandey, 2023). However, there is a scarcity of studies investigating the precise pathways through which organizational gaslighting influences vital outcomes like job satisfaction and psychological resilience (Katsiroumpa et al., 2025; Kukreja & Pandey, 2023).

Concurrently, gender continues to be a critical contextual factor affecting job satisfaction, with studies revealing nuanced interactions influenced by socio-economic status, workplace policies, and work-life balance measures (Farid et al., 2024). These gender dynamics have yet to be fully integrated into the understanding of how gaslighting impacts employees differently, pointing to a significant gap in intersectional research (Güleç & Özbay, 2024; Majumdarr et al., 2024).

Given these gaps, this study aims to examine the relationships between organizational gaslighting, gender, and job satisfaction, focusing on the direct impact of gaslighting on job satisfaction and exploring gender as a potential moderator in this

relationship. Through this, the study seeks fill the gap and aims to provide actionable insights for developing gender-responsive organizational policies and interventions that enhance psychological safety and promote sustained job satisfaction.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the present study are the following:

- To examine the relationships among Trivialization, Affliction, Gender, and Job Satisfaction among employees
- To investigate the predictive roles of Trivialization, Affliction, Gender, and Job Satisfaction among employees
- To assess the moderating effect of gender on the relationship between Trivialization, Affliction, and Job satisfaction among employees

Research Hypotheses

This study aims to test following hypotheses:

- H1: Trivialization will be negatively associated with job satisfaction among employees.
- H2: Affliction will be negatively associated with job satisfaction among employees.
- H3: Gender will moderate the relationship between Trivialization and job satisfaction.

Figure 1: Hypothetical Model

Methodology

Research Design and Sampling Strategy

The research design employed in this study was a correlational cross-sectional design. A sample of 401

adults, consisting of both males and females, was recruited from various organizations. In addition to this, a non-probability convenience sampling technique was used. However, the study sample did

not include any individuals who were mentally or physically disturbed.

Assessment Measures

The Workplace Gaslighting Scale (WGS), developed by Kukreja and Pandey (2023), is a self-report measure designed to assess gaslighting behaviors exhibited by supervisors toward subordinates in the workplace. The scale consists of 12 items rated on a Likert-type scale, with higher scores indicating greater exposure to gaslighting behaviors. Psychometric evaluation through exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis confirmed the two-dimensional structure of the scale. The scale demonstrated strong internal consistency, with Cronbach’s alpha coefficients of 0.86 for the Trivialization subscale and 0.842 for the affliction subscale.

Job Satisfaction was measured using a simple self-report item asking participants to rate their overall satisfaction with their current job. Responses were recorded on a 3-point rating scale (1 = dissatisfied, 2 = neutral, 3 = satisfied), allowing for a straightforward assessment of general workplace contentment. Gender was recorded as a categorical variable with participants marking themselves as either male or female to allow for analysis of gender differences across study variables.

Procedure of Data Collection

Online methods were used to gather the data, particularly a customized Google form. The form's design took into account a number of significant factors, such as preventing incomplete submissions, prohibiting multiple inputs from the same email

address, and inserting a consent form at the start of the inquiry. Participants were given a brief explanation of the study's objectives before giving their informed consent. Participants were thanked for taking part after completing the questionnaire.

Ethical Considerations

Permission from the original author of the scale was obtained before using it for the study variables. In addition to this, institutional approval was also secured. Participants provided informed consent, acknowledging the voluntary nature of their participation. They were informed that they could withdraw their data at any point in time without facing any consequences. Throughout the study, strict measures were implemented to safeguard participant confidentiality.

Results

The present study examined the reliability, validity, and predictive relationships among Affliction, Trivialization, gender, and job satisfaction. Preliminary analyses were conducted to assess the measurement model, including reliability and validity checks. Structural model analyses were then performed to test the hypothesized associations and interaction effects. Specifically, results are presented in four parts: (a) reliability and convergent validity of the study constructs, (b) discriminant validity of the measurement model, (c) interaction effects of gender with Affliction and Trivialization on job satisfaction, and (d) the explained variance in job satisfaction.

Table 1: Reliability Analysis

Variables	Cronbach’s α	AVE
Affliction	0.8	0.17
Trivialization	0.86	0.13

Note. AVE = Average Variance Extracted.

Table 1 presents the reliability estimates for the study variables. Cronbach’s alpha values indicated acceptable internal consistency for Affliction ($\alpha = .80$) and Trivialization ($\alpha = .86$). However, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values were below the recommended threshold of .50, suggesting limited convergent validity for both constructs.

Table 2 Discriminant Validity - Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Affliction	-					
2. Gender	0.14	-				
3. Job Satisfaction	0.06	0.18	-			
4. Trivialization	0.97	0.08	0.04	-		
5. Gender × Affliction	0.19	0.06	0.09	0.18	-	
6. Gender × Trivialization	0.27	0.08	0.10	0.21	0.82	-

Table 2 shows discriminant validity, a reflective construct should have the strongest correlations with its own indicators in comparison to any other construct, according to the discriminant validity

evaluation (Hair et al., 2022). Recommended criteria for discriminant validity is less than 0.9 (Ringle et al., 2023). Results reported adequate discriminant validity between the study variables.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Table 3 Interaction effect

Path coefficients	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	t-statistics	P values
Gender x Affliction -> Job Satisfaction	0.006	0.203	0.585	0.558
Gender x Trivialization -> Job Satisfaction	-0.006	0.212	0.735	0.462

Table 3 shows the results of the interaction effects on job satisfaction. Neither interaction term was statistically significant. Specifically, the interaction between Gender and Affliction did not predict job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.006, t = 0.585, p = .558$), nor did

the interaction between Gender and Trivialization ($\beta = -0.006, t = 0.735, p = .462$). These findings suggest that gender does not moderate the relationships of Affliction or Trivialization with job satisfaction.

Table 4 R-square

Variable	R-square	R-square adjusted
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Job Satisfaction	0.054	0.042
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Table 4 presents the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the model predicting job satisfaction. The predictors explained 5.4% of the variance in job satisfaction ($R^2 = .054$), with an adjusted R^2 of .042. This indicates that the model accounted for only a small proportion of variance, suggesting limited explanatory power.

Figure 3: Structural Model

Discussion

This study aimed to examine the relationships among Trivialization, Affliction, Gender, and Job Satisfaction and to evaluate gender's moderating role. Hypothesis 1 proposed a negative association between Trivialization and Job Satisfaction. However, our results did not provide significant empirical support, consistent with earlier findings highlighting the complex and sometimes indirect influence of perceived Trivialization or undervaluation on satisfaction (Xie & Sun, 2021). Hypothesis 2 expected a negative relationship between Affliction and Job Satisfaction, but this was also not statistically significant, which may reflect measurement limitations as that other psychosocial factors (e.g., social support, organizational trust) exert stronger influence on satisfaction (Garmendia et al., 2023). Hypothesis 3 posited that Gender would moderate these relationships; however, interaction effects were non-significant, aligning with studies suggesting gender differences may not universally moderate job attitudes (Aurangzeb et al., 2023).

Conclusion

Workplace gaslighting by supervisors has a profound negative effect on job satisfaction, as it fosters an environment of mistrust, confusion, and emotional distress. This psychological manipulation undermines employees' confidence, impairs their engagement,

and reduces their overall satisfaction with their roles. Addressing workplace gaslighting is crucial for safeguarding employee well-being and organizational health. Future research should investigate the long-term impacts of gaslighting and protective factors such as social support and resilience. Practically, organizations need to implement clear policies, provide training to promote ethical leadership, and create safe reporting systems to effectively prevent and mitigate gaslighting, thereby enhancing job satisfaction and workplace climate.

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